

Archive Management at Bpjs Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office

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ABSTRACT

Archive Management at BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office. This research uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. This research was carried out at BPJS Employment Gorontalo Branch Office. Data sources in this study consist of primary data and secondary data. Data collection techniques through observation, structured interviews, and documentation. This data analysis is carried out inductively based on empirical evidence, including: Data Reduction, Data Presentation, and conclusion or verification of Records Management, at the BPJS Employment Branch Office in Gorontalo City which is seen from human resource factors, archive classification, and archival infrastructure facilities are still not optimal in supporting archives at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office. Therefore, the need for additional employees (contract labor), additional facilities and special attention by the head of BPJS in providing facilities and employee needs.

INTRODUCTION

Records management is an activity or process that includes recording, controlling, storing, maintaining, supervising, transferring and destroying, which in its implementation must be supervised and directed so that archives as information centers can be used optimally. The purpose of archives, namely sources of information and materials for accountability if at any time the document is needed, in this case as a support for smooth administrative activities. However, based on observations in the field, there are still several things that are problems in managing records at BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch, namely:

- a. lack of human resources, in this case as an archive manager at BPJS Employment only has 1 employee in managing archives, this certainly makes records management not optimal so that many archives are still messy such as scattered, incomplete signatures of officers and officials on duty or improper numbering of records, which makes these files cannot be archived.
- b. the lack of optimal classification of archival data, this can be seen from the number of archives that are not sequential according to year, alphabetical and BPJS Employment activity programs every year so that it often makes it difficult for employees to find back the required documents.
- c. lack of archive storage infrastructure, in this case seen from the archive storage area that is still lacking, including the room where the archives are very small, cabinets, shelves, and order-order folders are still limited so that the archives have not been neatly arranged in place and also still look very damp walls. Therefore, researchers conducted a study to find out and analyze the management of records at the BPJS Employment Office Gorontalo City Branch.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Office Administration

According to (nurhikmahyanti, 2021: 4) in the Modern Office Management Book, office administration is all activities carried out in the framework of office administration business to assist organizational leaders in decision making and achieving organizational goals. According to (Sutha, n.d. 2018: 6-7), office administration is a series of structuring activities for the main work carried out by a group of people in a form of cooperation to achieve certain goals. According to George R. Terry in the book management and control (1996) quoted from (Halimah, 2018: 25), defines office management includes planning, controlling, and organizing office work, as well as mobilizing those who carry out in order to achieve predetermined goals.

Management

According to John F. me in (Dewi, 2021: 3), management as an art to make minimal efforts to secure maximum prosperity and maximum happiness for business owners and employees and provide the best service for the community. According to (Bararah 2020: 351), management is an activity carried out together and through people and groups with a view to achieving organizational goals.

According to Malayu S.P Hasibuan quoted from (Ichsan, 2019: 14), management is the science and art of managing the process of utilizing human resources effectively, which is supported by other sources in the organization to achieve certain goals. According to George R. Terry quoted from (Ichsan, 2019: 14), that management is a process consisting of planning, organizing, controlling, which is carried out to determine and achieve predetermined goals through the use of natural resources and others.

Archive

According to The Liang Gie (2009: 118) quoted from (Dan et al., 2014: 552), archives are collections of instruments that are stored systematically because they have uses so that whenever needed they can be quickly reused.

Records Management

According to Law no. 43 of 2009 quoted from (Wardah, 2016: 60), records management is the process of controlling dynamic records effectively, efficiently, and systematically including the creation, use, and maintenance, as well as depreciation of archives. According to (Febriana 2020: 129), the management of these records must be guided by four main pillars of archives which include:

1. Official scripture, namely the management of information which includes types, media, formats, security, provision, legal, distribution, and storage in official communications.
2. Classification of archives, namely the pattern of organizing information systematically and logically as the basis for archival filing.
3. Archive retention schedule, which is a list containing the period of storage of records, types of records, and information containing recommendations for determining records to be destroyed or permanent. Records retention schedules are used as guidelines in the valuation and depreciation of records.
4. Archive security and access classification system, namely grouping records based on the impact on the interests and security of the state, public, and individuals, to then be compiled as a basis for arrangements that protect the rights and obligations of archive creators legally and facilitate the use of archives by the public.

Human Resources

According to Tinangon, Kojo and Tawas (2019) in (Suparyanto and Rosad 2020: 1), HR is the design of formal systems in an organization to ensure the effective and efficient use of human talent to achieve organizational goals.

Facilities and Infrastructure

According to Sopian (2019: 44) Facilities and Infrastructure are everything that can be used as a tool in achieving goals or objectives (tools / media).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

This research uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. This research was conducted at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo Branch Office. Data sources in this study consist of primary data and secondary data. Informants who became the object of research, interviewed there were 7 informants, namely: Head of General Affairs & Human Resources (1 person), Head of Participation (1 person), General Associate Administrator (1 person), Service Associate Administrator (1 person), Finance Section (1 person), Special Account Representative (1 person), Special Participant Administration Officer (1 person). Data collection techniques through observation, structured interviews, and documentation. This data analysis is carried out inductively based on empirical evidence including: Data Reduction, Data Presentation, and conclusions or verification.

RESULTS

Resources

The resources referred to in this study are those related to archival officers whether they can manage archives properly in supporting the administrative process. The results of an interview with the informant (RU) as the Head of Participation, said that:

"Archives are actually one of the important things in a company, so they have to be checked and monitored as well as files and all kinds of things, so I think

resources are very important people, so there must also be someone in the archives section to manage these archives." (interview July 18, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that human resources in the archive are needed to maintain and manage existing files, in order to support company activities and smooth administration. The results of an interview with an informant (MAJ) as the Associate Director of Service, said that:

"For us, the resources are actually sufficient and indeed prepared properly, so at BPJS Employment itself the archives are managed by archival officers. But this year the position of archival officer is still vacant, so the archives are still managed by their respective fields." (interview July 19, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the position of archival officer is very important, and each field should work according to its own proxy. From the informant's statement above, the author can conclude that the vacancy in the position in the job makes the job taken over by each so that the responsibility is delegated to their respective fields.

The results of an interview with informants (ZV) as the Head of General Affairs and Human Resources, said that:

"The filing officer at BPJS Employment is still vacant, until now no one has filled the position, the vacancy in HR at archiving does make it difficult so that the responsibility is borne by their respective fields to archive it." (interview on July 21, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, the author can conclude that no human resources for archiving at BPJS Employment are occupied, making it difficult to archive data or files carried out in their respective fields at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan. Based on the results of the study, researchers can conclude that human resources in the BPJS Employment filing section are still empty, making it difficult for employees to archive the document files carried out, because the person in charge of archiving is empty to do the archiving.

Archive Classifier

The classification of archives referred to in this study is related to the pattern of archival arrangements whether they are in accordance with the numbers, letters, and programs in the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch. The results of an interview with the informant (MY) as the Associate General Officer, said that:

"With my own knowledge as a general associate administrator, the classification in BPJS is very detailed where the special archive of guarantees has a guarantee archive code, if it is a special archive for participation, registration, or invitation letter for cooperation, the code is participation, as well as operations have their own archive classification so it is very detailed and regulated in the archives directors, and already meets the standards." (interview July 18, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the classification of archives at BPJS Employment has gone well, where each program has its own archive code and has run according to standards. The

results of an interview with informants (RU) as the Head of Participation, said that:

"This archive is if in BPJS Employment we are divided into fields, there are in the fields of participation, finance, services, if in my own field of participation, there are usually several classifications, based on company segments and active non-active segments. For example, in the company's wage earner segment, there is an active archive, namely companies that are still participants in BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, and we save all the files until the company is inactive and then moved again. The classification itself is still a bit messy, but it is up to standard." (interview July 18, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the classification in BPJS Employment is quite detailed, this can be seen from the statement that distinguishes between active and inactive company segments. However, even though it meets the standards, researchers consider that the maximum archive classification has not been created which causes the archives to be scattered / messy.

The results of an interview with an informant (MAJ) as the Associate Director of Service, said that:

"If the classification of archives is indeed in BPJS Employment, the classification of archives already exists starting from what type of archive it is, whether it is for memos, internal memos or external memos or incoming letters or outgoing letters, there is already its own classification, even it is a field, so for example from the field of participation there is its own classification or letter code, then in the field of service there is also its own letter code classification, the archive code, So the classification of archives has indeed been completely adjusted to the field according to the type of archive. However, even though the classification has been arranged in detail, there are still a few shortcomings, which sometimes employees can misclassify archives, for example archive numbers that are arranged incorrectly, archived letters that have not been completed, either from the officer's signature, or some letters that are still separate." (interview July 19, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the classification in BPJS Employment is quite optimal because it is regulated in detail related to the types of archives, which of course can make archives quickly found again when needed, but sometimes errors can come from their own human resources.

The results of an interview with informants (INGN) as PPK, said that:

"For the classification of records in BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, it is very clear, from the classification of letters, there are arrangements that regulate and have met the standards, so in the arrangements we are quite good in the arrangements, if it is not done based on standards, it will be difficult for us if we will look for old archives." (interview July 19, 2023)

Based on the results of the research above, the researcher concluded that archiving at BPJS Employment has been carried out based on the provisions that have been set, so that the search for documents that have been archived will be easily done. The classification of records carried out by employees in

their respective fields is in accordance with the archiving provisions in the BPJS Keteanagakerjaan Gorontalo City Branch.

Archive Facilities and Infrastructure

The facilities and infrastructure referred to in this study are facilities / places to support archives in BPJS Employment Gorontalo City. The results of the interview with informant (B) as the Finance Department, said that:

"For the facilities and infrastructure that are appropriate, we already have an archive room and the filing is appropriate, but sometimes we lack folder boxes and file cabinets, so that making archives stacked, so that it will be interlude in archiving files that will only be archived, although it does not always happen but it can make difficulties in archiving." (interview July 18, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that infrastructure facilities are still lacking or not optimal in supporting archives. Because folders are one of the factors that need to be considered also archive storage. The results of an interview with informants (RU) as the Head of Participation, said that:

"This infrastructure facility is more of a facility or place, so this infrastructure must indeed support it too, because we store files in physical form, meaning we must need a room that is in accordance with the specifications, so that the files stored can be durable and not damaged, in BPJS Employment itself the facilities and infrastructure are quite supportive and so far the problem that I have found in archival facilities and infrastructure is the difficulty of archives being found." (interview July 18, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, especially the Gorontalo City branch itself, has provided sufficient facilities for archives, but there are still some things that cannot be overcome, such as archives are difficult to find again. The results of an interview with an informant (MAJ) as the Associate Director of Service, said that:

"If the actual facilities and infrastructure are for now, because we see that the current office is still a rental office, for the facilities there is no separate archive warehouse in this office, but we have another archive office that we rent specifically for placement or archive management. However, when it becomes a new office, there is a room prepared specifically for archives. So for adequate facilities and infrastructure, and sufficient for archive management, it's just that it is currently separate from our office, and so far the problems I have faced are related to archive facilities and infrastructure, for example file A is stored in file B." (interview July 19, 2023)

From the results of the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the facilities and infrastructure of the archives at BPJS Employment Gorontalo City are adequate, it's just that currently the office where the archives are used to store archives is a rented office, this is because the official office is still under construction, besides the problems that occur about misplacing the archive.

The results of an interview with informants (INGN) as PAPK, said that:

"For facilities and infrastructure, if in each field it is enough, but not maximized because sometimes we lack a folder box for archiving letters so it will be difficult for us to make archives, what else if we stack documents to be archived, it is difficult for us to archive them." (interview July 19, 2023)

From the results of the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that the facilities and infrastructure of archives at BPJS Employment are sufficient, but there are still things that need to be improved. The results of the interview with the informant (AT) as the Special Account Representative, said that:

"For the Gorontalo City BPJS Employment facility for archiving already exists, such as there is a dokumen storage building that has been kept at temperature in the storage building so that it is not damp so that documents are maintained not eaten by termites, because the main problem is termites, especially documents stored are prone to termites, besides that we also provide document storage cabinets and folders even though sometimes we sometimes lack folders for archiving storage." (interview July 21, 2023)

From the results of the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that archival facilities and infrastructure at BPJS Employment are available, especially in providing archival buildings that are maintained at the temperature in the room so that they are not easily damp so that documents are well maintained and not eaten by termites.

Based on the results of the above research, researchers can conclude that a special building or special room is provided for archive storage, so that archiving items owned by the Gorontalo City branch of BPJS Employment can already be stored in buildings that have been dedicated to archiving, but there are still shortcomings in storage cabinets and folder boxes, so sometimes archiving can be stacked for storage.

DISCUSSION

Human Resources

Human resources in archive management are still less than only one person, so archives are only managed by each field. is still very lacking. What needs to be done by the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City is to increase human resources in archive management, which can be done with contractual cooperation. Because considering archives is one of the most important things in the company, namely as a source of memory and to support the administrative process, the archives must be managed very well. Human Resources is one of the most important factors that cannot even be separated from an organization, as explained by Astri Dwi Andriani, et al. (2022: 14), human resources are the most important factor in an organization, because they are the determining factor for success in running the wheels in the organization, one of which is as a defense guard. According to Eri Susan (2019: 954) Human Resources are productive individuals who work as drivers of an organization.

Classification of Archives

The classification in this study is related to the pattern of arrangement or procedures for storing and organizing archives according to the same several

categories. In the category of archive classification systems, several codes / codes are given, namely the number system (numeric), letter system (alphabets), letter and number combination system (alphanumeric), problem system (subject), date system (chronology), and regional system (geographic). Classification of archives is intended to be able to recognize the activities and problems contained in letters / archives. The classification of archives in the Gorontalo City Employment BPJS can be said to be good and has met the standards, it's just that one of the things that is the problem is that there are still records that are stored inappropriately which might happen from employees who manage these records. According to Mulyono et al (2011: 105) quoted from (Dan et al., 2014: 552), that archives are records of activities or events in various forms and media in accordance with the development of information and communication technology made and accepted by state institutions, regional governments, educational institutions, companies, political organizations, community organizations, and individuals in the implementation of community, nation, and state life.

Archive Facilities and Infrastructure

The facilities and infrastructure of the archives at BPJS Employment Gorontalo City are good enough but cannot support all existing archives because there is still a lack of folders and cabinets to store documents. What should be done by BPJS Employment Gorontalo City is to pay attention to things that are still lacking in archive storage, such as folders that should be checked continuously for availability because Purwanto n.d. (2019: 4) Infrastructure is a supporting facility that can support the process in administrative activities. According to Ilham Kamaruddin n.d. (2022: 59), Infrastructure is a tool that has an important role in a process in order to achieve success and achievement in the final result. Facilities and infrastructure can also be interpreted as facilities that are absolutely fulfilled to provide convenience in carrying out an activity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Records Management at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office as seen from human resource factors, classification of archives, and archive infrastructure facilities is still not optimal in supporting archives at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office. Therefore, it is necessary to add employees (contract labor), so that the management of records at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office can be carried out optimally. In addition, the need for initial inspection before the archive is stored, so that the archives at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office can be arranged according to their respective codes, names and types. The need for additional facilities in the form of folders and cabinets so that archives do not accumulate and are neatly arranged, to anticipate if one day archives are needed, they are quickly found again. And there needs to be special attention by the head of BPJS in providing facilities and employee needs in archiving so that the archived data will be easy to store and fast in searching for data.

FURTHER STUDY

In this study, researchers only studied Records Management at the BPJS Employment Gorontalo City Branch Office in terms of human resources, classification of archives, and archival infrastructure. Therefore, further researchers can add other factors that also affect archive management.

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